

MicrogridSpy Analysis for Electrification of Kalibote Village in Mozambique

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Keywords

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Executive Summary

The Government of Mozambique is conducting the development of The Mphanda Nkuwa project, it is a large-scale hydroelectric power plant estimated to produce 1,500 MW of electricity. It involves building a dam and power station on the Zambezi River, 60 kilometers downstream from the existing Cahora Bassa dam and power plant (2075MW). The project is estimated to cost 4.5 billion euros and is expected to be operational by 2031.

To implement this project, rural communities directly affected by the project were identified, hence the need to electrify these communities using sustainable photovoltaic solar energy solutions, thus promoting the socioeconomic development of these areas and improving the quality of life of the local populations.

For this study, the Kalibote Village (Lat. -15,638367; Long 32,962374), Cahora Bassa District, Tete Province, was selected.

To model the electrification of this village Microgridspy and Ramp tools were applied to determine the technologies and the best configuration that provides the most favourable cost for achieving electricity access in that location.

The modelling results indicate that to achieve better results, a combination of Solar Panels + Batteries + Diesel Generator with a total investment cost of 159,22 kUSD, Total Variable Cost of 55,15 kUSD, Total Fixed O&M Cost 4,48 kUSD, Total Battery Replacement Cost 6,17 kUSD, Total Fuel Cost 44,49 kUSD and Total Salvage Value 27,58 kUSD.

Key Findings

This hybrid setup offers the most cost-effective and reliable energy supply for the village, due to the best-performing configuration of Solar Panels + Batteries + Diesel Generator. And the hybrid system leverages the low operating cost of solar and batteries while using the diesel generator for reliability during peak or low-sunlight periods.

The salvage value of 27.58 kUSD indicates potential asset recovery at the system's end-of-life, enhancing overall cost-effectiveness.

The results support a balanced approach between renewable energy and dispatchable backup generation, enabling reliable electricity access with manageable long-term costs.

1. Introduction

The Mozambican government has been actively promoting renewable energy initiatives, particularly solar photovoltaic (PV) solutions, to enhance electricity access in rural areas. Despite these efforts, a significant portion of the population, over 40%, remains without reliable electricity, highlighting the ongoing challenges in expanding energy infrastructure and services. The Mozambican government has set a goal of achieving universal access to energy by 2030. This ambition is outlined in the "Energia para Todos" (Energy for All) initiative and aims to provide all Mozambican households with sustainable and affordable electricity. The government is focusing on expanding on-grid infrastructure and implementing off-grid solutions, particularly through solar home systems, mini-grids, and clean cooking solutions.

Having identified communities that could be affected by the implementation of the Mphanda Nkuwa hydropower project, and to promote the socioeconomic development of these areas and improve the quality of life of the local populations, the need for electrification in these areas is urgent, given that many communities still depend on traditional energy sources, such as firewood and kerosene, which pose serious risks to health and the environment. The electrification of the communities will allow access to essential services, such as education, health and security, as well as support local productive activities.

Objective and aims

- To assess the energy needs of a neighbourhood in the districts of Cahora Bassa, Tete Province.
- To propose viable solutions for electrification based on solar photovoltaic systems.
- To ensure that the proposed solutions are financially accessible and technically appropriate to local conditions, with due integration into the socioeconomic reality of the communities.

2. Methodology

The study involved a survey of the infrastructure and energy needs of Kalibote community with support from community leaders, geographic mapping of the areas was carried out, surveys with the local population were conducted, solar data was downloaded from EU PVGIS to calculate the solar generation capacity of the location and determine the viability

of the solar technology ensuring that the proposed solutions meet energy needs efficiently and sustainably.

To model the energy needs, Microgridspy was used, an open-source energy optimization tool developed to assist in the planning, sizing, and operation of rural and off-grid microgrids, particularly in remote or underserved areas.

As methodology for the study, the CESP framework was used:

- Analyzing the context of the action in terms of regulatory framework and local energy needs;
- Grouping available resource and energy demand assessments;
- Supporting the identification and the sizing of adequate technical solutions;

To run the scenarios, the following parameters were considered:

Data collection for load demand assessment analysis

The Kalibote Village is located in (Lat. -15,638367; Long 32,962374), Cahora Bassa District, Tete Province, and the following user groups were identified and classified:

Total Population	845
Number of Dwellings	169
• Low income	154
• Lower middle income	15
Barba shop	1
Shop	1
School	1
Public lighting	12

Assumptions

The table shows the loads that were considered for each category of users

User Category	Appliances												
	Indoor and Outdoor Bulb	Torch Flashlight	Phone Charger	TV	Decoder	Refrigerator	Freezer	POS	Laptop	Printer	Hair Clippers	Hair Dryer	Pub Lights
Low Income	•	•	•										
Lower Middle Income	•	•	•	•	•	•							
School	•		•						•	•			
Barba Shop	•		•								•	•	
Shop	•		•	•	•	•	•	•					
Public Lighting													•

Scenario Selection

Tree scenarios were selected

Scenarios	System	Constrain	Load
Scenario 1	PV Battery Generator	No Renewable Penetration Constraint	Partial Load activated
Scenario 2	PV Battery Generator	Minimum Renewable Penetration: 95%	Partial Load activated
Scenario 3	PV Battery	100% Renewable	

1st Scenario

In this scenario, it was selected a system using PV + Battery and a Generator. The current load in the village was considered for the first year, and a load growth rate increase of 3% yearly until the fourth year and on the fifth year, an increase of new category users and appliances, namely, Mills, Fan and Ion, with high electricity consumption, on diesel generator partial load was activated and in addition no renewable energy penetration was introduced.

2nd Scenario

As in the first scenario, the same assumptions were made, with the difference that in this scenario, a renewable energy penetration of 95% was considered.

3rd Scenario

In this scenario, it was selected a system using PV plus Battery only. The current load in the village was considered for the first year, and a load growth rate increase of 3% yearly until the fourth year.

3. Results

Scenario Analysis

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
	PV + Battery + Generator	PV + Battery + Generator	PV + Battery
	No RE penetration	95% RE penetration	100% RE Penetration
	Partial Load Activated	Partial Load Activated	
kUSD			
NPC	86.79	115.02	154.10
Total Investment Cost	59.22	149.28	232.83
Total Variable Cost	55.15	35.26	29.70
- Total Fixed O&M Cost	4.48	9.67	15.12
- Total Battery Replacement Cost	6.17	14.44	14.58
- Total Fuel Cost	44.49	11.15	
Total Salvage Value	27.58	69.52	108.43
<u>Levelized Cost of Energy USD/kWh</u>	<u>0.3992</u>	<u>0.5291</u>	<u>0.7088</u>
Total Installed Capacity			
Solar kW	22	65	102
Batteries kWh	61	160	269
Generator kW	7	3	

The study evaluated three scenarios, and the first scenario presents the lowest Net Present Cost, which includes the total variable costs and consequently the minimum total salvage value at the end of the useful life of the project.

In scenario 2, with the introduction of renewable energy penetration at 95%, it has implications of an additional 25% of the total project cost.

For scenario 3 with 100% of RE penetration, the NPC of the project is high compared to other scenarios, nevertheless, the project is better for the climate and energy transition.

5. Discussion

The first scenario, with the following results **Solar PV: 61.2%**, **Battery: 61.2%** and **Diesel Generator: 26.3%** tells us that this system has a high reliance on **Solar PV** and **Battery**, meaning renewable energy and storage and the **Diesel Generator** still contributes significantly, possibly as backup during periods of low solar generation or high demand.

The second scenario with **Solar PV: 67.4%**, **Battery: 31.3%**, **Diesel Generator: 1.3%** suggest that the system relies even more heavily on **Solar PV**, indicating improved solar resource utilization or larger solar capacity, **Diesel use is minimal**, signaling a shift towards cleaner energy and perhaps better system design for renewables, battery usage remains important, likely for load shifting and stability.

The third scenario **Solar PV: 68.7%**, **Battery: 31.3%**, **Diesel Generator: (0%)** shows that this configuration is **completely diesel-free**, representing an ideal renewable system. Battery support is still crucial, highlighting the need for adequate storage when relying on intermittent renewables like solar.

7. Conclusion

Among the three scenarios investigated, the PV+Battery+Diesel Generator option, with an investment cost of 59,22 kUSD and a LCOE of 0.3992 USD/kWh, emerges as the most financially favourable solution. In contrast, the PV+Battery option entails a significantly higher investment cost of 232,83 kUSD and a LCOE of 0.7088 USD/kWh.

From scenario 1 to 3, there is an Increased Solar Integration: Solar PV's share rises from 61.2% to 68.7%, showing a trend toward greater renewable penetration. **Diesel Phase-Out:** The gradual elimination of the diesel generator from 26.3% down to 0% reflects the policy goals of the Government of Mozambique for decarbonization of the energy sector and Battery usage remains relatively stable (~31–61%), underlining its importance in enabling high renewable penetration by storing excess solar energy and stabilizing supply.

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References

National Electrification Strategy, 2018

Electrification Plan for Off-Grid Areas, Resolution n. ° 52/2023

Energy Transition Strategy, Resolution n. ° 61/2023

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